

Supplementary Material

Sex-Related Communicative Functions of Voice Spectral Energy in Human Chorusing

Peter E. Keller, Jennifer Lee, Rasmus König, & Giacomo Novembre

This document contains supplementary material consisting of (1) detailed methods, (2) acoustic analyses of stimulus items, and (3) detailed results for statistical analyses of listener judgements in the online sensitivity and preference studies.

Stimulus files for individual audio excerpts, raw data from the sensitivity and preference online listening studies, and scripts for statistical analyses are available as part of the electronic supplementary material at: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.jh9w0vthn>

1. Methods

1.1 Participants

Sensitivity and preference for the enhanced singer's formant were examined in separate online listening studies. Recruitment and data collection took place during non-overlapping timeframes for the two studies, and individual participants took part in only one of the studies.

For each study, participants were initially recruited via social media, online forums, sites for research participation, advertisements in music newsletters and media outlets, and personal contacts in amateur music-related organizations including choral societies, school groups, and university departments. These initial recruitment drives took place via separate sets of such sources in 2016 and 2017 for the preference study and in 2018 for the sensitivity study. Additional recruitment was done via Amazon's crowdsourcing platform, Mechanical Turk (www.mturk.com), for both studies in 2019. Individuals who were recruited in the initial drives participated voluntarily without any compensation. Participants recruited via MTurk received financial compensation (a fixed amount of \$3 USD) for their time. No participant selection criteria were imposed apart from having access to an electronic device with a web browser, internet connection, and audio capabilities.

Our stopping rule for data collection was to meet a target response rate of 1000 or more valid data sets per study. A total of 1354 people (774 females and 580 males) completed the sensitivity study and 1374 people (788 females and 586 males) completed the preference study. As is recommended practice in online studies [1], quality control screening procedures were implemented to identify datasets with invalid responses (see Data Analysis section for details). We also restricted the final analysis to participants who were aged 12 years or more (corresponding to the youngest members of the choir that produced the stimuli). The final participant sample in the sensitivity study consisted of 679

females (median age = 24 years; range 12-71 years) and 481 males (median age = 29 years; range 17-81 years). The final sample for the preference study consisted of 655 females (median age = 24 years; range 13-78 years) and 432 males (median age = 28 years; range 12-86 years). 296 female and 127 male participants in the sensitivity study had four or more years of formal musical training and 327 female and 177 male participants had such training in the preference study. None of the participants reported hearing impairments that prevented them from doing the tasks.

Note that we refer to biological sex (female or male) rather than gender primarily because our hypotheses were based on biological sex in non-human species. Therefore, the relevant question included in our online surveys was “What is your sex?” and the response options were “Female” or “Male”. It is possible that participants interpreted the question as referring to gender, which may have added noise in the data to the extent that people’s gender identities differ from their biological sex. This issue, along with sexual orientation (which was not assessed), deserve to be addressed in future research.

The project was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee at Western Sydney University (protocol number H10487). Participants provided informed consent by clicking a virtual button after a welcome screen in the online platform informed them about the topic of the study and what they would be required to do. The online studies were publicly available and participation was unrestricted, and hence minors could potentially access them. Therefore, an item was added that asked whether the prospective participant was under 18 years of age. If the individual indicated that they were under 18 years, they were informed that parental consent was required for participation, and a Parental Consent Form was presented. The form requested the parent to indicate by button click that the child consents to participate and the parent consents to the child’s participation.

1.2 Study design

The sensitivity study tested the ability of female and male listeners to identify which item from pairs of excerpts of choral performances of a homophonic Chorale and a polyphonic Fugue were sung to an audience in which girls were present (as opposed to an exclusively male audience). The independent variables were listener sex (female or male) and musical piece (Chorale or Fugue), and the dependent variable was the percentage of excerpt pairs in which listeners selected the correct item (i.e., the excerpt sung with girls in the audience).

The preference study assessed which item from the same pairs of excerpts were preferred by female and male listeners. The independent variables again were listener sex (female or male) and musical piece (Chorale or Fugue), and the dependent variable was the percentage of pairs in which listeners selected the excerpt sung with girls in the audience.

Listener age, musical experience, cultural background, and stimulus item (there were multiple excerpts per musical piece; see below) were included as covariates in the experimental design, but were not themselves of theoretical interest. Musical experience was operationalized as binary variables reflecting formal musical training (musicians with four or more years of training vs non-musicians) and choral singing experience (some vs none). The 4-year cut off for musical training was set based on the lower bound of the

inter-quartile range of split points identified in a survey of published studies comparing musicians and non-musicians [2].

Cultural background was crudely operationalized as a binary variable based on whether the participant had spent more time living in a European country or another country (which we assumed to be potentially relevant given that the musical stimuli represented the European choral tradition). The cultural background classification took into account the participant's country of birth and the country in which they spent most time living. Participants who were born and spent most time living in a European country (i.e., on the European continent) were classified as 'European', participants who were born and spent most time living elsewhere were classified as 'non-European,' and the remaining participants (i.e., those born in Europe but living elsewhere, or born elsewhere but living in Europe) were classified as 'mixed'.

1.3 Materials

The same set of audio stimuli was used in the sensitivity and preference study. This stimulus set included 12 pairs of items consisting of audio excerpts from performances of two distinctive pieces of choir music—a homophonic Chorale and a polyphonic Fugue—sung by an elite boys choir to audiences in which girls were present or absent. An additional stimulus item was used as a practice trial and another additional item was used to check the reliability of listener adjustments across repeated presentations.

The Chorale and the Fugue, which are representative of Western sacred music, were composed by Johann Sebastian Bach (1685-1750) for a four-part choir setting comprising soprano, alto, tenor, and bass voices. The Chorale “Du heilige Brunst, süßer Trost [You holy zeal, sweet consolation]” is from the motet “Der Geist hilft unser Schwachheit auf [The Spirit gives aid to our weakness]” (BWV 226), and was written in 1729, is in quadruple meter (4 quarter-note beats per bar), and has a stately “reverent” character. The Fugue is part of the motet “Singet dem Herrn ein neues Lied [Sing unto the Lord a new song]” (BWV 225), and was first performed around 1727, is in triple meter (3 eighth-note beats per bar), and has a “lively” character. The Chorale's homophonic texture emphasizes the overall harmonious sound and requires rhythmic unison and strict synchrony between parts, whereas the Fugue's polyphonic texture emphasizes individual parts and is characterized by greater rhythmic independence between parts.

The data collection protocol and detailed analyses of the original performances are reported in a previously published article [3]. The singers were 16 members of the St. Thomas Choir of Leipzig in Germany: Four sopranos, aged 12 (n=2) and 13 years (n=2); four altos, aged 12 (n=2), 13 (n=1), and 16 years (n=1, singing falsetto); four tenors, aged 16 (n=2) and 18 years (n=2); four basses, aged 16 (n=1), 17 (n=2), and 19 years (n=1). A senior member of the choir (aged 18 years) conducted the performances. The girls included in the audience were aged 15-16 years. All performers and audience members were unaware of the purpose of the original study.

The performances were recorded with head-worn wireless microphones (Sennheiser ME 3) fitted to each choir member and with two digital video cameras (Sony HDR-HC9). Our previous study [3] focused on individual boys' voices and therefore analyzed audio from

the head-worn microphones. The current study focuses on the overall choir sound and therefore used audio from one of the cameras, which was positioned at the rear of the auditorium (behind six rows of tiered seating) facing the choir. Audio was recorded in .WAV format for the performances of the two musical pieces via the camera's inbuilt microphone in stereo at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz and 16 bits per sample.

The items used in the current study were extracted from full recordings of the choir in Audacity software. First, the performances were segmented into phrases based on musicological analysis by authors RK and PEK. This resulted in 18 excerpts with durations ranging from 3.13 s to 7.58 s for the Chorale, and 20 excerpts with of 4.30-8.42 s duration for the Fugue. All excerpts were converted to 44.1 kHz stereo .MP3 files (i.e., the format required by the online platform that was used for the listening studies).

Next, the proportion of spectral energy in the 2500-3500 Hz singer's formant region of each excerpt was computed via audio analysis using the MIR Matlab toolbox [4]. The parameters for the analysis were the same as in Keller et al. (2017), although in that previous study, the pipeline was applied to audio recordings of full performances separately for each of the 16 singers' voices, whereas in the current study, the analysis was done on short excerpts from the recording of the full choir (in order for the analysis to apply the identical signal that would be presented to participants).

The pool of potential stimulus items was subject to a selection procedure that entailed ordering the excerpts by the amount of energy in the 2500-3500 Hz region. Two experimenters and a research assistant listened to all the potential items to identify recordings with noise that could prove distracting or otherwise influence listener judgments. Five potential stimulus items (three Chorale excerpts and two Fugue excerpts) were eliminated due to the presence of such noise. From the remaining set, the top six items for each piece were chosen as the final 12 stimulus items. The next highest items from the Chorale were selected as additional items for a practice trial and a reliability check.

The final set of stimulus items was analyzed using audio signal processing techniques to test for acoustic differences between excerpts from the two pieces sung with girls present versus absent. Our hypotheses for the listening studies centered on differences in spectral energy in the 2500-3500 Hz singer's formant region of the choral sound and, therefore, to exclude other potential factors that could influence listener judgements, we analyzed the duration of the excerpts and their total acoustic energy (see Analyses of Audio Stimuli section below). These acoustic analyses confirmed that energy in the singer's formant region was higher for excerpts sung with girls present for both pieces (which is unsurprising given that this was a feature of the source materials), and additionally revealed that the effect was reliably stronger for the Chorale than the Fugue (see Figure 1A-C in article, where panels A and B show frequency spectra with the Terhardt outer ear modelled applied [5]). There were no statistically significant effects of the presence of girls or musical piece on excerpt duration or total acoustic energy, indicating that these features do not reliably provide potential cues to differentiate performances sung with girls present or absent.

1.4 Procedure

The sensitivity study and the preference study were both conducted using the Qualtrics online survey platform (<https://www.qualtrics.com>). Participants accessed each study remotely on their own individual devices via a URL internet link provided in the recruitment postings.

On the study website, participants were presented with an information page that specified what they would be asked to do, followed by a consent form, and then a page with detailed instructions. The general procedure was the same in both studies and only the instructions about listener judgements differed. In the sensitivity study, participants were informed that they would be presented with pairs of short excerpts from two live concerts, that girls were present in the audience for only one of the concerts, and that the task was to listen to both excerpts and to indicate which excerpt was more likely to come from that concert. For the preference study, participants were only informed that they would be presented with pairs of short excerpts from two live concerts, and that the task was to indicate which performance they preferred. Participants were told that there was no time limit for the task, and that they could listen to the excerpts as many times as required. The use of headphones or earphones was recommended.

Prior to the main listening task, participants were presented with an example item (from the Chorale, but containing a different pair of excerpts than the test items) so that they could familiarize themselves with the task and adjust the sound settings to a comfortable loudness level. For the test items that followed, participants were presented a text prompt (which differed depending on the question for the two tasks), a media player that they could control, and two response options—Performance 1 or Performance 2—that they could choose from by clicking on a virtual button.

In the main listening task, each of the 12 pairs of test excerpts played automatically when loaded (though participants were free to listen to it more times by using the media controller). Stimulus items were blocked by musical piece (Chorale and Fugue), with block order randomized across participants. Presentation order of the six pairs of excerpts (Chorale or Fugue) within each test block was also randomized. The order of items within each pair was fixed, with excerpts from performances sung with girls present occurring as the first item in three pairs, and as the second item in three pairs, for each musical piece.

The additional item that was intended as a reliability check was used in the sensitivity study and for the version of the preference study run via MTurk (but not in earlier versions). This item was presented three times—before the first test block, between test blocks, and after the second test block—to provide a means for assessing the consistency with which an individual was responding.

Following the listening task, a background questionnaire was presented. The questionnaire items asked participants about their age, sex, hearing health, musical experience, and country where they were born, spent most time, and currently reside. With regard to musical experience, the questions addressed whether or not participants had received formal musical training and, if so, how many years. Participants were also asked

whether they had experience with choir singing. The background questionnaire was deliberately brief to increase the likelihood that participants would complete it.

All participants in the sensitivity study were asked to indicate whether they used headphones/earphones while doing the task. These participants, and individuals who participated in the MTurk preference study, were also given the opportunity to provide open-ended comments about the study in a text dialog box. They were invited to use this response to mention features of the performance that influenced their judgements. For the sensitivity task, participants were then shown a score indicating how many instances of performances sung in the presence of girls they correctly identified. The procedure for both tasks took, on average, around 10 minutes to complete.

1.5 Data analysis

Raw data from both online studies were downloaded from Qualtrics in .csv format, sorted by a Matlab script, and then complete datasets were imported into R (version 4.3.1) within RStudio (version 2023.06.1+524) for analysis. Data from individuals who indicated that they were younger than 12 years or older than 90 years were excluded from analysis (0.4% of the sample for the sensitivity study and 0.2% for the preference study). The analysis procedure was identical for each study.

The first step entailed implementing quality control measures that took into account (1) the duration taken to complete the task for both studies, (2) the consistency of responses to the repeated item that was included as a reliability check (note that this information was not available for all participants in the preference study), and (3) whether headphones were used in the sensitivity study (this information was not collected in the preference study). Data from individuals who took less than 5.5 minutes to complete the study were removed, amounting to the loss of 190 datasets for the sensitivity study and 284 datasets for the preference study. This filtering criterion was established based on estimates of the minimum time required to do the task diligently by two of the authors.

Filtering based on consistency of responses to the repeated reliability check item (i.e., the same response for all three presentations of the item) led to large amounts of data attrition (leaving only 447 participants for the sensitivity study and 222 participants for the preference study). In hindsight, we realized that the reliability check might not have been a fair test because the difference in energy in the singer's formant region is relatively small between excerpts in the reliability check item. Nevertheless, we conducted a preliminary analysis on the sensitivity data to test whether accuracy at selecting the excerpt with the enhanced singer's formant (i.e., sung with girls present) was related to consistency across the reliability check items. Accuracy scores for test items were not normally distributed (Shapiro-Wilk's test $p < 0.05$), and therefore a nonparametric Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test was used. This analysis revealed that accuracy for test items did not differ significantly between participants who passed the reliability check ($n = 447$; median percent correct = 50% [mean = 53.58%], range = 8.33-91.67%) and those who did not ($n = 713$; median = 50% [mean = 54.08%], range = 8.33-100%) [$W = 162024$, $p = 0.60$, Effect size = 0.0143, 95% CI [0.001, 0.070]. This result supports our contention that the reliability check was perhaps not a fair (or relevant) test and we therefore decided to include all participants in the main analyses for each study.

With regard to headphone usage, 700 participants reported that they listened through headphones/earphones, 457 reported that they did not use such devices, and three participants did not respond to this item. Reported headphone usage was higher among male listeners (72%) than female listeners (53%) [$\chi^2(1) = 7.1, p = 0.008$]. Analysis of the sensitivity data indicated that, although response accuracy on the sensitivity task was numerically higher for participants who reported using headphones (median = 58.33% [mean = 54.14%], range = 8.33-91.67%) than for those who did not (median = 50% [mean = 53.67%], range = 8.33-100%), this difference was not statistically significant [$W = 154346, p = 0.30$, Effect size = 0.0300, 95% CI [0.002, 0.090]]. We did not include headphone usage as a factor in subsequent analyses.

Prior to running the main analyses of listener sensitivity and preference, we screened the data for outliers and tested whether data were normally distributed and whether the homogeneity of variances assumption was met. No extreme outliers were identified (using the 'identify_outliers' function from the rstatix R package) for sensitivity and preference grouped by listener sex and piece. Shapiro-Wilk's tests revealed that sensitivity and preference scores were not normally distributed for females or males in either piece ($ps < .05$). Despite differences in sample sizes for female and male participant samples, Levene's test indicated that variances in sensitivity and preference scores were not significantly different for female and male listeners for either piece ($ps > 0.05$).

Sensitivity to, and preference for, the enhanced singer's formant was tested in three steps. First, one-sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank tests were used to compare listener judgements (percentage of items where excerpts with enhanced singer's formant were selected) against chance-level performance (50%). Non-parametric tests were used due to the data being not normally distributed. These tests were conducted on all data pooled (averaged across musical pieces), separately for the sensitivity and preference study.

The second analysis step used binomial Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) analyses, which were run using the 'glmer' function from the lme4 R package (version 1.1-34), to examine effects of listener sex (female or male) and piece (Chorale or Fugue) on listener judgements for each test item. The dependent measure in these analyses consisted of each participant's raw scores, comprising binary values indicating whether (1) or not (0) she or he selected the excerpt with the enhanced singer's formant in each of the 12 test items (6 for the Chorale and 6 for the Fugue). The binomial GLMM approach was motivated by the fact that scores, based on the percentage of excerpts with the enhanced singer's formant that were selected, were not normally distributed in the sensitivity study or the preference study (Shapiro-Wilk's test $ps < 0.05$). Moreover, using binomial GLMMs allowed us to test the effects of listener sex and piece on listener sensitivity and preferences while controlling for other factors in the regression models. Additional factors that were entered into the models included age, musical training, choir experience, and cultural background.

The analysis strategy in each study entailed testing three successively complex GLMMs that included fixed factors and random effects, and then comparing the explanatory power of these full models to one another and to a reduced model that contained only the random effects. The first, and simplest, full model included listener sex and musical piece as fixed

factors and participant (represented by unique numerical codes) and test item (also represented by unique codes) as random effects. The second full model was similar to the first but included participant age and musical training (musician or non-musician) as additional fixed factors. The third full model went further by additionally including experience with choir singing (some or none) and cultural background (European, non-European, or mixed) as fixed factors. The cultural background classification took into account the participant's country of birth and the country in which they spent most time living. Participants who were born and spent most time living in a European country (i.e., on the European continent) were classified as 'European', participants who were born and spent most time living elsewhere were classified as 'non-European,' and the remaining participants (i.e., those born in Europe but living elsewhere, or born elsewhere but living in Europe) were classified as 'mixed'.

Finally, following the GLMM analysis of data in each study, four Wilcoxon signed rank tests were run separately for female and male participants, and separately for the Chorale and the Fugue piece. Bonferroni correction was applied to the criterion for statistical significance in these four tests (critical alpha = $0.05/4 = 0.0125$).

2. Analyses of Audio Stimuli

Here we present analyses of audio files used as stimuli in two online listening studies. The tasks required male and female participants to make perceptual judgments of brief excerpts from choir performances of two pieces, a homophonic Chorale and a polyphonic Fugue, sung with girls present or absent from the audience. Stimuli were presented in pairs that included one excerpt that had been sung with girls present and the other with girls absent (either as the first or second item within a pair). There were six such pairs for the Chorale and six for the Fugue.

One study focused on listener sensitivity, testing whether participants could detect which excerpt in each pair was sung with girls present. The other study addressed listener preferences by asking participants to indicate which excerpt they preferred in each pair. The present analyses apply audio signal processing techniques to the stimulus items to quantify potential acoustic differences between excerpts sung with girls present versus absent. The motivation for these analyses was to quantify objective features that could be used by listeners as cues when making perceptual judgements. Our hypothesis was that spectral energy in the 2500-3500 Hz singer's formant region of the choral sound would be influential. Keller, König, and Novembre [3] analyzed additional features related to performance tempo, total acoustic energy, and relative note-onset timing (a measure reflecting ensemble coordination) in the full performances, and found that these measures did not reliably differentiate performances sung with and without girls present. Our current analyses focused on energy in the singer's formant region, excerpt duration (as a proxy for tempo, which is difficult to estimate reliably with brief items), and total acoustic energy.

2.1 *Singer's formant*

The first analysis compared energy in singer's formant region for excerpts of performances sung with girls present versus absent. The data are displayed in Table S1, where it can be seen that the percentage of energy in the singer's formant region was greater when girls were present than absent for each stimulus pair. The difference scores are normally distributed across excerpts ($p > 0.05$) for each piece, as assessed by Shapiro-Wilk's test of normality (Chorale: $W = 0.853$, $p = 0.166$; Fugue: $W = 0.933$, $p = 0.607$). There was homogeneity of variances between the two pieces, as assessed by Levene's test ($p = 0.678$).

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted on these data to test for effects of audience (girls present, girls absent) and musical piece (Chorale, Fugue) on the proportion of energy in the singer's formant range. Audience was treated as a repeated measures factor and piece was considered as a between-groups factor. The ANOVA revealed statistically significant main effects of audience ($F_{1,10} = 134.53$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.93$) and a significant interaction between audience and piece ($F_{1,10} = 18.76$, $p = .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.65$). The main effect of piece was not statistically significant ($F_{1,10} = 0.98$, $p = .346$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.09$).

Table S1: Percentage of spectral energy in the 2500-3500 Hz ‘singer’s formant’ region of the audio signal from the full choir for stimuli used in the online listening studies. The percentage of energy in the singer’s formant region was greater when girls were present than absent for each excerpt, as indicated by the positive (+) difference scores in rightmost column.

Piece	Excerpt	Energy in Singer’s Formant Region (%)		Difference (Present – Absent)
		Girls Present	Girls Absent	
Chorale	1	6.93	5.90	+1.03
	2	10.83	8.68	+2.15
	3	6.53	4.32	+2.22
	4	9.37	6.87	+2.49
	5	10.12	7.85	+2.27
	6	11.31	9.52	+1.79
	Mean	9.18	7.19	+1.99
	SE	0.75	0.71	0.20
Fugue	1	8.60	8.01	+0.59
	2	7.95	6.99	+0.96
	3	8.62	7.25	+1.37
	4	7.12	6.32	+0.80
	5	6.07	5.50	+0.57
	6	8.29	7.13	+1.16
	Mean	7.77	6.86	+0.91
	SE	0.37	0.32	0.12

The main effect of audience indicates that energy in the 2500-3500 Hz singer’s formant region was generally higher when girls were present than absent. This is unsurprising given that stimuli were selected based on this property. It is, however, noteworthy that this effect was qualified by the interaction between audience and piece, indicating that the enhancement of the singer’s formant when girls were present was greater for the Chorale than the Fugue. Nevertheless, paired-samples t-tests confirmed that the effect of audience was statistically significant separately for both the Chorale ($t_5 = -9.32, p < .001$) and the Fugue ($t_5 = -7.00, p < .001$).

2.2 Duration

The durations of the audio files are shown in Table S2. The duration difference scores are normally distributed (Shapiro-Wilk’s test $p > 0.05$) for each piece and there was homogeneity of variances between the two pieces (Levene’s test $p > .05$). An ANOVA with a similar design to the earlier analysis of energy in the singer’s formant range was conducted on these data. The ANOVA yielded no statistically significant effects of

audience ($F_{1,10} = 1.65$, $p = .228$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.14$), piece ($F_{1,10} = 3.30$, $p = .099$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.25$), or the interaction of these factors ($F_{1,10} = 0.95$, $p = .352$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.09$). Therefore, although durations of excerpts varied, these variations were not systematically related to whether or not the excerpts came from performance sung with girls present or the particular musical piece.

Table S2: Duration of the audio files used as stimuli in the online listening study. The stimuli consisted of six excerpts from a homophonic chorale and a polyphonic fugue sung with girls present or absent from the audience. There were no systematic differences in duration between performances with girls present or absent (see the main text for details), indicated by the mix of positive (+) and negative (-) difference scores.

Piece	Excerpt	Duration (s)		Difference (Present – Absent)
		Girls Present	Girls Absent	
Chorale	1	3.91	4.09	-0.18
	2	3.70	3.54	+0.16
	3	4.98	4.98	0.00
	4	4.01	3.88	+0.13
	5	5.60	5.58	+0.03
	6	5.76	5.97	-0.21
	Mean	4.66	4.67	-0.01
SE	0.34	0.37	0.06	
Fugue	1	5.24	5.16	0.08
	2	4.35	4.45	-0.10
	3	4.35	4.43	-0.08
	4	6.54	6.60	-0.05
	5	7.77	8.14	-0.37
	6	8.08	8.14	-0.05
	Mean	6.06	6.15	-0.10
SE	0.62	0.64	0.05	

2.3 Total energy

Total acoustic energy of the stimulus files was assessed by computing the root-mean-square (RMS) of the audio signal amplitude (i.e., taking the root average of the square of the amplitude) using the MIR Matlab toolbox [4]. The total energy for each audio file is shown in Table S3. Total energy difference scores are normally distributed (Shapiro-Wilk's test $ps > 0.05$) and there was homogeneity of variances (Levene's test $p > .05$). An ANOVA on these data yielded no statistically significant effects of audience ($F_{1,10} = 0.48$, $p = .503$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.05$), piece ($F_{1,10} = 0.70$, $p = .422$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.07$), or the interaction of audience and piece ($F_{1,10} = 0.32$, $p = .583$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.03$). Thus, although energy in the singer's formant range varied as a function of these factors, total energy did not. This finding

suggests that total energy cannot be used as a reliable potential cue to differentiate performances sung with girls present.

Table S3: Total energy for the audio files used as stimuli in the online listening study. Total energy was assessed by computing the root-mean-square of the amplitude of the audio signal (in arbitrary units). There were no systematic differences in total energy between performances with girls present or absent (see the main text for details), indicated by the mix of positive (+) and negative (-) difference scores.

Piece	Excerpt	Total Energy (RMS Amplitude)		Difference (Present – Absent)
		Girls Present	Girls Absent	
Chorale	1	0.2048	0.2199	+0.0151
	2	0.1641	0.1551	-0.0090
	3	0.2302	0.2350	+0.0048
	4	0.2125	0.2164	+0.0039
	5	0.2402	0.2414	+0.0013
	6	0.2263	0.2242	-0.0021
	Mean	0.2130	0.2153	+0.0023
SE	0.0101	0.0115	0.0030	
Fugue	1	0.1945	0.1948	+0.0003
	2	0.2001	0.2065	+0.0063
	3	0.2050	0.2018	-0.0032
	4	0.2032	0.2066	+0.0034
	5	0.2168	0.2158	-0.0010
	6	0.2039	0.1994	-0.0045
	Mean	0.2039	0.2041	+0.0002
SE	0.0027	0.0027	0.0015	

3. Detailed results for listener judgments

Details of statistical analyses of listener judgements in the sensitivity and preference online studies are reported in this section. These analyses used Generalized Linear Mixed Models (GLMMs) to examine the explanatory power of different fixed factors (listener age, musical training, choir experience, and cultural background, in addition to listener sex and musical piece) and random effects (participant and test item) on sensitivity and preference data. Wilcoxon signed rank tests were used to compare sensitivity and preference scores to chance-level performance.

3.1 Sensitivity

Three successively complex GLMMs were run to test the degree to which different combinations of fixed factors and random effects could predict listener sensitivity responses for test items with and without an enhanced singer's formant. The dependent measure in these analyses consisted of each participant's raw data, comprising binary values indicating whether (1) or not (0) she or he selected the excerpt with the enhanced singer's formant in each of the test items.

The first, and simplest, full model included listener sex and piece as fixed factors and participant (represented by unique numerical codes) and test item (also represented by unique codes) as random effects: $\text{Sensitivity} \sim \text{Sex} * \text{Piece} + (1 | \text{Participant}) + (1 | \text{Item})$.

The second full model was similar to the first but included listener age and musical training (musician or non-musician) as additional fixed factors: $\text{Sensitivity} \sim \text{Sex} * \text{Piece} * \text{Age} * \text{Musical Training} + (1 | \text{Participant}) + (1 | \text{Item})$.

The third full model went further by additionally including experience with choir singing (some or none) and cultural background (European, non-European, or mixed) as fixed factors: $\text{Sensitivity} \sim \text{Sex} * \text{Piece} * \text{Age} * \text{Musical Training} + \text{Choir Experience} + \text{Cultural Background} + (1 | \text{Participant}) + (1 | \text{Item})$. Choir experience and cultural background were included to control for overall effects of these variables and interactions with the other fixed factors were not tested.

A reduced model that contained only the random effects was also tested: $\text{Sensitivity} \sim 1 + (1 | \text{Participant}) + (1 | \text{Item})$.

The outcome of each GLMM analysis is shown in Table S4. The amount of variance accounted for by each model (estimated using Nakagawa's R-squared values [6]) was generally small and there were no statistically significant predictors of listener sensitivity. The quality of the four models was compared based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) using the AICtab function from the bbmle package [7]. The results presented in Table S5 suggest that the second and third models have similar likelihood of being the best-supported model, with Akaike weights indicating that the third model is only 1.02 times more likely to be the highest quality model than the second model. However, these two models are superior in this respect relative to the remaining models. For example, the second model is 17.17 times more likely than the first model, and 2.21 times more likely than the random model, to be the superior model. Therefore, models including listener sex,

musical piece, listener age, and musical training as fixed factors have higher goodness-of-fit than models consisting of only listener sex, musical piece, and random effects, even when the greater number of parameters is taken into account. The lack of statistically significant individual predictors in these models suggests that listener sensitivity may rely on basic perceptual abilities.

Table S4: Output of the full GLMMs with listener sensitivity as the dependent variable and listener sex, musical piece, listener age, musical training, choir experience, and cultural background as fixed factors and participant and test item as random effects. Output for a reduced model with only random effects is also shown. Values are estimates ('Est.') of slope coefficients and Z statistics. Estimates of variance accounted for and model fit statistics are displayed at the bottom of the table. Conditional R-squared takes fixed and random effects into account, whereas marginal R-squared only considers fixed factors.

	Reduced Model		Full Model 1		Full Model 2		Full Model 3	
	Est. (SE)	Z	Est. (SE)	Z	Est. (SE)	Z	Est. (SE)	Z
(Intercept)	0.163 (0.093)	1.76	0.282 * (0.126)	2.24	0.232 (0.129)	1.80	0.281 * (0.132)	2.13
Listener Sex			-0.012 (0.053)	-0.23	-0.042 (0.065)	-0.65	-0.059 (0.065)	-0.90
Musical Piece			-0.247 (0.177)	-1.39	-0.236 (0.181)	-1.31	-0.236 (0.181)	-1.31
Sex x Piece			0.039 (0.070)	0.55	0.097 (0.087)	1.11	0.097 (0.087)	1.11
Age					0.078 (0.052)	1.50	0.075 (0.052)	1.44
Musical Training					0.156 (0.092)	1.69	0.120 (0.093)	1.29
Sex x Age					-0.019 (0.069)	-0.27	-0.017 (0.069)	-0.24
Piece x Age					-0.044 (0.070)	-0.63	-0.044 (0.070)	-0.63
Sex x Musical Training					0.043 (0.115)	0.37	0.042 (0.115)	0.36
Piece x Musical Training					-0.046 (0.124)	-0.37	-0.046 (0.124)	-0.37
Age x Musical Training					-0.029 (0.084)	-0.35	-0.037 (0.084)	-0.44
Sex x Piece x Age					-0.041 (0.092)	-0.44	-0.041 (0.092)	-0.44
Sex x Piece x Musical Training					-0.131 (0.154)	-0.85	-0.131 (0.154)	-0.85
Sex x Age x Musical Training					0.027 (0.109)	0.25	0.026 (0.109)	0.24

Piece x Age x Musical Training			0.204 (0.113)	1.80	0.204 (0.113)	1.80
Sex x Piece x Age x Musical Training			-0.201 (0.146)	-1.37	-0.201 (0.146)	-1.37
Choir Experience					-0.076 (0.041)	-1.82
Cultural Background (Mixed)					0.048 (0.136)	0.35
Cultural Background (European)					0.102 (0.067)	1.51
<hr/>						
N observations	13,920	13,920	13,920	13,920	13,920	13,920
Conditional R2	0.048	0.049	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.050
Marginal R2	NA	0.004	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007
Log Likelihood	-9,459	-9,458	-9,443	-9,440	-9,440	-9,440
AIC	18,924	18,928	18,922	18,922	18,922	18,922
BIC	18,947	18,973	19,058	19,058	19,081	19,081
Deviance	18,461	18,461	18,462	18,462	18,467	18,467
Df Residual	13,917	13,914	13,902	13,902	13,899	13,899

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

Table S5: Results of model comparison using AIC, ordered from lowest (best) to highest (poorest) for analyses of the listener sensitivity study. The dAIC measure indicates the difference in AIC from the minimum-AIC model and the weight value represents an estimate of the likelihood of a model being the best-supported one within the set of compared models.

Model	AIC	dAIC	df	weight
Full Model 3	18,922.3	0	21	0.402
Full Model 2	18,922.4	0	18	0.395
Reduced Model	18,924	1.6	3	0.179
Full Model 1	18,928	5.7	6	0.023

One-sample Wilcoxon signed rank tests were used to compare sensitivity scores to chance-level performance (50%) for data pooled across listener sex and averaged across musical pieces, and separately for females and males for the Chorale and the Fugue. Basic statistics are reported in the main manuscript and additional statistics are reported here in Table S6.

Table S6: Results of Wilcoxon tests against chance (50%) for sensitivity scores (percentage of test items where participants selected the excerpt with an enhanced singer’s formant). Confidence intervals are for effect sizes obtained via bootstrapping (with 1000 replications) using the `wilcox_effsize` function from the `rstatix` R package.

Test (vs chance)	V	Effect Size <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pooled Data	277274	0.23	< .001	0.18	0.29
Chorale					
Females	79800	0.28	< .001	0.21	0.35
Males	38815	0.31	< .001	0.22	0.39
Fugue					
Females	57710	0.06	.071	0.00	0.14
Males	32554	0.04	.418	0.00	0.14

3.2 Preference

As with the sensitivity data, three successively complex GLMMs were run to test the degree to which different combinations of fixed factors and random effects could predict listener preferences responses. The dependent measure consisted of binary values indicating whether (1) or not (0) the participant selected the excerpt with the enhanced singer’s formant in each test items.

Again, the first full model included listener sex and piece as fixed factors and participant and test item as random effects: Preference ~ Sex * Piece + (1 | Participant) + (1 | Item). The second added age and musical training as fixed factors: Preference ~ Sex * Piece * Age * Musical Training + (1 | Participant) + (1 | Item). The third full model added choir experience and cultural background as fixed factors: Preference ~ Sex * Piece * Age * Musical Training + Choir Experience + Cultural Background (1 | Participant) + (1 | Item).

The outcome of each GLMM analysis is shown in Table S7, where it can be seen that, although the amount of variance accounted for by each model was small, listener sex was a statistically significant predictor of preferences in each full model. As a caveat, it should be noted that all models were singular, and this issue was not resolvable by removing terms or using different optimizers. Singularity notwithstanding, model comparison using AIC (Table S8) revealed that the first model had the highest likelihood of being the best-supported model, with Akaike weights indicating that it is 3.25 times more likely to be the highest quality model than the reduced model (with random effects only) and over 100 times more likely than the other full models. There was a statistically significant main effect of listener sex on preference scores in this best-fitting model, indicating that female listeners were more likely than male listeners to select the excerpt with an enhanced singer’s formant. The main effect of musical piece and the interaction between listener sex

and musical piece were not statistically significant, suggesting that female preferences for the enhanced singer's formant generalized across the two pieces.

Table S7: Output of the full GLMMs with listener preference as the dependent variable and listener sex, musical piece, listener age, musical training, choir experience, and cultural background as fixed factors and participant and test item as random effects. Output for a reduced model with only random effects is also shown. Values are estimates ('Est.') of slope coefficient and Z statistics. Estimates of variance accounted for and model fit statistics are displayed at the bottom of the table.

	Reduced Model		Full Model 1		Full Model 2		Full Model 3	
	Est. (SE)	Z	Est. (SE)	Z	Est. (SE)	Z	Est. (SE)	Z
(Intercept)	0.085 (0.104)	0.82	-0.003 (0.150)	-0.02	-0.057 (0.154)	-0.37	-0.033 (0.157)	-0.21
Listener Sex			0.133 ** (0.051)	2.60	0.144 * (0.070)	2.06	0.140 * (0.070)	1.99
Musical Piece			0.057 (0.212)	0.27	0.051 (0.218)	0.23	0.051 (0.218)	0.23
Sex x Piece			-0.067 (0.073)	-0.92	-0.055 (0.099)	-0.55	-0.055 (0.099)	-0.55
Age					0.091 (0.048)	1.91	0.096 (0.049)	1.96
Musical Training					0.101 (0.082)	1.24	0.095 (0.084)	1.13
Sex x Age					-0.130 (0.068)	-1.90	-0.133 (0.069)	-1.92
Piece x Age					-0.073 (0.068)	-1.07	-0.073 (0.068)	-1.07
Sex x Musical Training					-0.020 (0.105)	-0.19	-0.019 (0.105)	-0.18
Piece x Musical Training					0.050 (0.116)	0.43	0.050 (0.116)	0.43
Age x Musical Training					-0.085 (0.075)	-1.15	-0.090 (0.075)	-1.19
Sex x Piece x Age					0.112 (0.097)	1.16	0.112 (0.097)	1.16
Sex x Piece x Musical Training					-0.062 (0.149)	-0.42	-0.062 (0.149)	-0.42
Sex x Age x Musical Training					0.113 (0.103)	1.10	0.119 (0.103)	1.16
Piece x Age x Musical Training					-0.020 (0.106)	-0.19	-0.020 (0.106)	-0.19
Sex x Piece x Age x Musical Training					-0.030 (0.146)	-0.20	-0.030 (0.146)	-0.20

Choir Experience				-0.025 (0.040)	-0.61
Cultural Background (Mixed)				-0.088 (0.116)	-0.76
Cultural Background (European)				-0.030 (0.045)	-0.67
<hr/>					
N observations	13,044	13,044	13,044	13,044	
Conditional R2	0.037	0.038	0.039	0.039	
Marginal R2	NA	0.001	0.002	0.002	
Log Likelihood	-8,852	-8,848	-8841	-8,841	
AIC	17,710	17,708	17719	17,723	
BIC	17,733	17,753	17853	17,880	
Deviance	17,650	17,642	17629	17,627	
Df Residual	13,041	13,038	13026	13,023	

*** p < 0.001; ** p < 0.01; * p < 0.05.

Table S8: Results of model comparison using AIC, ordered from lowest (best) to highest (poorest) for analyses of the listener preference study. The dAIC measure indicates the difference in AIC from the minimum-AIC model and the weight value represents an estimate of the likelihood of a model being the best-supported one within the set of compared models.

Model	AIC	dAIC	df	weight
Full Model 1	17708.1	0	6	0.761
Reduced Model	17710.4	2.4	3	0.234
Full Model 2	17718.6	10.5	18	0.004
Full Model 3	17723.4	15.3	21	<0.001

One-sample Wilcoxon signed rank tests were used to compare preference scores against chance (50%) for data pooled across listener sex and averaged across musical pieces, and separately for females and males for the Chorale and the Fugue. Basic statistics are reported in the main manuscript and additional statistics are reported here in Table S9.

Table S9: Results of Wilcoxon tests against chance (50%) for preference scores (percentage of test items where participants selected the excerpt with an enhanced singer's formant). Confidence intervals are for effect sizes obtained via bootstrapping (with 1000 replications) using the `wilcox_effsize` function from the `rstatix` R package.

Test (vs chance)	<i>V</i>	Effect Size <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Pooled Data	220124	0.15	< .001	0.09	0.21
Chorale					
Females	59954	0.16	< .001	0.09	0.24
Males	21661	0.01	.928	0.00	0.11
Fugue					
Females	57862	0.15	< .001	0.08	0.22
Males	23514	0.06	.190	0.00	0.15

Supplementary References

- 1 Buchanan, E. M., Scofield, J. E. 2018 Methods to detect low quality data and its implication for psychological research. *Behavior Research Methods*. **50**, 2586-2596. (10.3758/s13428-018-1035-6)
- 2 Zhang, J. D., Susino, M., McPherson, G. E., Schubert, E. 2020 The definition of a musician in music psychology: A literature review and the six-year rule. *Psychology of Music*. **48**, 389-409. (10.1177/0305735618804038)
- 3 Keller, P. E., König, R., Novembre, G. 2017 Simultaneous cooperation and competition in the evolution of musical behavior: Sex-related modulations of the singer's formant in human chorusing. *Frontiers in Psychology*. **8**, 1559. (10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01559)
- 4 Lartillot, O., Toiviainen, P., Eerola, T. 2008 A matlab toolbox for music information retrieval. In *Data analysis, machine learning and applications*. (eds. C. Preisach, H. Burkhardt, L. Schmidt-Thieme, R. Decker), pp. 261-268. Berlin: Springer.
- 5 Terhardt, E. 1979 Calculating virtual pitch. *Hear. Res.* **1**, 155-182.
- 6 Nakagawa, S., Johnson, P. C. D., Schielzeth, H. 2017 The coefficient of determination R² and intra-class correlation coefficient from generalized linear mixed-effects models revisited and expanded. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*. **14**, 20170213. (doi:10.1098/rsif.2017.0213)
- 7 Bolker, B. 2022 bbmle: Tools for General Maximum Likelihood Estimation (R package version 1.0.25) 1.0.25. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=bbmle>